

Tracing the Hiuen Tsang's Pilgrimage Route from China to the Ancient Punjab

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Amarbir Singh

Research Scholar
History Department
Panjab University
Chandigarh, Punjab, India

Abstract

The present paper is an attempt to assess the previous research conducted on Hiuen Tsang's travelogue. It analyses the various existing interpretations about the locations of various places of his visit and, juxtaposes its identification with assistance of the archaeological findings, Geographic Information System (GIS data) and environmental studies. The topographic features of the ancient Punjab observed and recorded by the traveller serves as indicators to trace the route of his journey. The traveller's route provides us new insights to explore the trade routes and, trade and urban centres of 7th century CE.

Keywords Tracing, Hiuen, Tsang, Pilgrimage, China, Ancient Punjab.

Introduction

Hiuen Tsang was a Chinese traveller who came to India to explore and fetch important records of Buddhism by visiting various places of religious importance. He set off on this pilgrimage in 639 CE. He entered India from its north-western frontiers. These frontiers lay up to eastern Afghanistan in 7th century CE. The Safed Koh Mountains and Hindukush Mountains in the Afghanistan acted as effective and extended frontiers respectively, forming a buffer zone between the Central Asia and the Indian subcontinent. After crossing Khyber Pass, a spur in the Safed Koh Mountains, he crossed the region of 'ancient Punjab' to proceed towards the Madhyadesh (or the mainland India). Historical records assigned various terms as the names of ancient Punjab such as 'Sapta-Sindhu' (in Rig Veda), 'Hapta-Hendu' (in Zend-Avesta), 'Pentapotamia' (in Greek sources) and 'Panchnada' (in the Mahabharata, Puranas and Patanjali's writings) which commonly indicates us towards its distinguished geographical characteristic i.e. the riverine system. Whereas, 'Vahika' and 'Aratta' (mentioned both in 'the Mahabharata and Panini's writings) are the names which attributed to its distinguished socio-cultural characteristics. All these names showcased the geographical extent of ancient Punjab in varying degrees. To the largest extent, the study of etymology of various names assigned to ancient Punjab reflects that it covers the area which lies between Hindukush range of Himalayas in the west to Yamuna River in the east; and from Pir Panjal range of Himalayas to the deserts of Sindh, Bahawalpur and Multan along with the lost tract of Ghaggar-Hakra River (ancient Saraswati River) in the south.

Aim of study

This study aims to explore the important urban centres and the land routes of ancient Punjab popular in the 7th century CE. Tracing the Hiuen Tsang, a Chinese traveller's route came to India at that time aims to throw light on such centres situated on his route. This study will open up further scope of research into the regional history with special reference to the trade and commerce.

Review of Literature

Alexander Cunningham's *The Ancient Geography of India* throws light on the geography of India rendered from the Greek historians' accounts and the travelogue of Hiuen Tsang. Hiuen Tsang's journey and his description of different places helps us to picturise the then landscape and the territorial extent of different states. This text gives us an overview of historical geography of India. However, a detailed study of regional importance to ancient Punjab is still not done.

T.W. Rhys Davids edited Thomas Watters's book *On Yuan Chwang's travels in India 639-645 AD* which traces the traveller's route which he opted from China to India, and back. This text provides us a chronological record of his complete journey. He crossed through the ancient Punjab twice during his expedition to the Indian subcontinent. His description about the various kingdoms of the Punjab gives us important information about the political history. However, a close correlation of the political history and the geography needs to be established which is missed out in this text.

Whereas, sincere attempts were made to find out recent research related to the topic of this research paper specially from 2021-23 but no study with direct linkage has been found.

Main Text

Early life of Hiuen Tsang

Amongst various Chinese travelers to the India, Hiuen Tsang is a man who presented most descriptive account of India. He was an avid scholar who resolved to travel to India to collect the holy records to complement the knowledge of Buddhism among the Chinese followers. He was given the title 'Master of the Law' due to his deep knowledge in philosophy and religious order. He was born in Chin-Lin village near modern Luoyang, Henan province, China. His grandfather Kong was appointed as president of the Imperial College at Peking due to his distinguished scholarship. The same intellectual capabilities were exhibited by his father which further travelled through genes to Hiuen Tsang himself. At the age of 8, his father identified his dedication towards reading books and acquiring new knowledge. Rather mixing with children of his age, he showed enthusiasm towards reading the scriptures of ancient sages. His elder brother Chang-Tsi taught him the method of reading and practice of sacred books of Buddhism. At the age of 13, he was admitted to the convent in Luoyang (the eastern capital of Chinese empire) as a recluse where he established his command on various records of the law and astonished the priests with his extra-ordinary memory and oratory. He shifted with his brother Chang-Tsi to the town of Shing-Tu after the fall of Sui dynasty. There, he was fully ordained as 'Master of the Law' after completing the age of 20. Going through the study of *Sutras and Sastras*, he raised some queries and to address these, he went out to meet different scholars and masters of these subjects. He travelled through the places i.e. Hang-Chow, Siang-Chow, Chiu-Chow and Chang'an or modern Xi'an (the western capital of Chinese empire). Visiting all these places and meeting the celebrated masters, he came to know that each of them implicated on the teaching of their school but, on verifying their doctrine, he observed that the holy books differed too much. He was determined to enrich his knowledge with most authentic sort of information. Thereafter, to clear his doubts, he resolved to travel towards the western world (India subcontinent) or the land of Buddha where the original holy books were produced.

Travel Route towards the Western World

Started his journey as a pilgrimage towards the western world in 639 CE, Hiuen Tsang transversed through the Chinese town of Tsin-Chow, Lan-Chow, Liang-Chow and Kwa-Chow. Further going westwards, he crossed the Takla Makan Desert and reached the town of I-Gu. Thereafter, he reached Kua-Chang (in modern district of Turfan of Xinjiang province).[1] Thomas Watters identifies Kua-Chang upto 640 CE as one among the 'western lands' (outside the control of Chinese Empire), which after the political turmoil of 639-640 CE, was taken under the imperial control by Chinese emperor Tai Tsung thence extending the western boundary of his empire upto Yenki (modern Karashar, Kyrgyzstan).[2]The pilgrim went through the towns namely Kuchih, Poh-lu-ka, Thousand Springs, Taras, Peh-shwi, Kong-Yu, Nujkend, Chaj, Ferghanah, Sutrishna, Samarkand, Bokhara, Khwarazm, Termez, Vakhsh, Baghlan, Balkh, Bamyan and Kapisa to reach the western frontiers of Indian subcontinent.[3] During his transit route, he crossed territories of modern nation-states of Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan and Afghanistan to enter into Indian subcontinent. From Kapisa (Afghanistan), he proceeded to Lamghan (Afghanistan) and Nagarahara or Jalalabad (Afghanistan). Nagarahara's natural boundaries were demarcated by Khyber Pass in the east, Jagdalak Pass in the west, Kabul River in the north and Safed-Koh Mountains in the south.[4]Geological studies suggests that the Safed-Koh Mountains are part of the western rim which separates the Indian tectonic plate from the Eurasian plate. The Khyber Pass (crossing spur of Safed-Koh Mountains) is regarded as 'the gateway to the Indian subcontinent' from the ancient times because of the easier accessibility through it. Khyber Pass has seen numerous migrations, movements of trade caravans and mobility of troops. Generally, Ancient Punjab covered the region to the east of Khyber Pass. However, the frontiers of Ancient Punjab encroached in and across Khyber Pass (even upto the eastern fringes of Hindukush Mountains) with the will and skill of regional and trans-regional rulers. Hiuen Tsang's pilgrimage transverse through the region of Ancient Punjab towards Ganga-Yamuna Plains and the rest of the India. S. Beal translates the Hwui Li's (Hiuen Tsang's disciple) work on the life of his teacher which have described the travel route and major

events of the pilgrim's travel throughout Indian subcontinent and his return to his homeland. The major places of his visit in a sequenced manner have been described in the below given lines. 'After crossing Khyber Pass, the pilgrim travelled through Gandhara, Utkhanda (Ohind), Swat, Taxila, Singapura, Urasa, Kashmir, Punch, Rajaori, Sakala, Lahore, Patti, Jalandhar, Kullu, Satadru, Mathura, Thanesar, Srughna, Kannauj, Koshambhi, Ayodhya, Sravasti, Kapilavastu, Kushinagara, Banaras, Vaishali, Patna, Bodh Gaya, Rajgriha, Nalanda. Thence, he penetrated the deep east through Modagiri, Champa, Pubna and Kamarupa. From Kamarupa (Assam), he turned southwards through Jessore, Tamralipti (Tamluk), Ganjam, Kalinga, Berar, Amravati and Kanchipuram (Tamil Nadu). However, he was willing to visit Ceylon (Sri Lanka) but, due to prevailing troublesome state of affairs due to king's death, he turned northwards via western coast of Indian Peninsula. He crossed Konkan coast to reach Bharoach, Ujjain, Vallabhi, Sindh and Multan (Pakistan). Thence, he once again turned towards east to Nalanda and Kamarupa. He started his westward journey in 643 CE towards Patliputra to join camp of King Harshavardhana and marched through Pryagraj, Koshambhi and Kannauj. From Kannauj, he took leave from Harshavardhana's camp to start his return journey to China, crossing through Punjab once again via Jalandhar and Utkhanda (Ohind). He further crossed Lamghan, Kabul, Ghazni and Kapisa. Going through Panjshir Valley, he reached Anderab, Khashgar, Yarkand, Khotan and finally in Luoyang in 645 CE.' [5]

Transversal through Ancient Punjab

Hiuen Tsang have described the northern division of India which comprised of the undivided Punjab, the Cis-Sutlej plains, Kashmir and adjoining hill states and the area beyond Indus River upto eastern Afghanistan. During Hiuen Tsang's visit in 7th century CE, northern India had three major powers with seats at Kapisa, Kashmir and Taki. Hiuen Tsang's Taki comprised the dissected foothills zone of Pir Panjal, Dhauladhar and Shiwalik ranges of Himalayas and plains between Indus and Beas rivers upto the junction of five rivers to the south-west of Multan. [6] The pilgrim has continuously used 'Taki' to define Punjab but somehow, he hasn't considered the Bist Doab and Cis-Sutlej area in it. It is worth mentioning here that, the pilgrim has defined 'Taki' as a politico-administrative unit. Whereas, in this study, we will take up a larger geographical unit, addressing it with 'Ancient Punjab'. As discussed earlier, the largest extent of ancient Punjab from west to east is reflected by the natural frontiers i.e. Hindukush mountains and Yamuna River respectively. However, be it the political control or the cultural cohesiveness, Khyber Pass parallel to the western watershed divide of Indus River most often remained the effective western boundary of ancient Punjab. Now let's discuss about the places which are visited by Hiuen Tsang comes under the preview of ancient Punjab (Refer to the Map 1).